

ICD-11 prolonged grief disorder: Prevalence, predictors, and co-occurrence in a large representative sample

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The International Classification of Diseases has recently defined Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) with symptoms such as longing, worry, and intense emotional pain that exceed sociocultural norms more than 6 months after the loss. This study aims to (a) estimate the prevalence of this new diagnostic category, (b) identify its sociodemographic and loss-related predictors, and (c) assess the co-occurrence of PGD with other psychological disorders and substance abuse. A large representative sample of Spanish adults ($N = 1498$) participated. Several multivariate binary logistic regression and multivariate logistic regression models were used. Results showed a 9.95% prevalence in the total sample. Catholic beliefs were a positive predictor, while higher income and more time since loss significantly decreased the odds of PGD. PGD significantly increased the likelihood of anxiety, depression, somatisation, post-traumatic stress disorder, loneliness and substance use. Our study contributes to assessing the multicultural PGD validity, as our results from a large representative sample are comparable to those in other countries with the PGDS. Our findings have direct implications for the assessment and treatment of bereavement, identifying for practitioners variables that make individuals more vulnerable to PGD. Results highlighted the high co-occurrence of PGD with other psychological illnesses and increased drug use.

Keywords: Prolonged grief disorder; International prolonged grief disorder scale; Risk factors; Prevalence; Comorbidity.

Losing a loved one is an emotionally painful and distressing experience that usually diminishes naturally over time. For some individuals, however, the distress is long-lasting and associated with functional impairment. The evident risk of pathologising a natural process has increased the difficulty of defining the disorder and determining when therapeutic help is needed. After several definitions, we are still in the long process of reaching an international conceptualisation of pathological grief based on scientific evidence and expert agreement (Killikelly & Maercker, 2017). Within this process of identifying maladaptive bereavement, the International

Classification of Diseases (ICD-11; WHO, 2018) has recently introduced Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). PGD is, therefore, a relatively new psychopathology included since 2018 in this classification. Diagnostic criteria include having at least one of two core symptoms, “persistent and pervasive longing” or “preoccupation” associated with the deceased, and also intense emotional pain (e.g., sadness, anger, guilt). Additionally, the grief response must last at least 6 months, exceeding sociocultural norms, and cause functional impairment.

Regarding the assessment of prolonged grief, a recent systematic review identified 11 different self-report scales

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(Trembl et al., 2020). Most of the scales had sufficient psychometric performance and could be used to assess the severity and cut-off score to screen maladaptive grief. However, none of the scales had items representing all the ICD-11 criteria for PGD, so this diagnosis could not be applied. Therefore, an accurate instrument was needed to capture each criterion of the ICD-11 PGD. Thus, the International Prolonged Grief Disorder Scale (IPGDS; Killikelly et al., 2020) was developed. The IPGDS is a self-report measure that assesses the ICD-11 PGD symptoms, comprised of 12 items that directly address the core grief symptoms and emotional pain, and the diagnostic criteria can be applied for caseness. It was designed for clinical practice and research, and it has been used to establish a PGD prevalence of between 6.9 and 37.5% in Switzerland, China, Portugal, and Germany (Killikelly et al., 2020). A recent study with this measure in the UK reported a PGD prevalence between 2.4 and 7.9% (Shevlin et al., 2023).

Several sociodemographic variables are associated with ICD-11 PGD, such as younger age, low income, or religiosity (Shevlin et al., 2023), female gender and fewer years of education (Lundorff et al., 2017). Furthermore, increased drug use has been reported as a way of coping with grief, as shown by a recent systematic review, which found that complicated grief predicted increases in tobacco and alcohol use and that drug addicts were at increased risk of developing complicated grief (Parisi et al., 2019). In addition, some variables related to the loss may complicate bereavement, such as a shorter time since the loss, a violent death, younger age of the deceased, and developing early PGD that may predict later PGD (Heeke et al., 2017).

Although most bereaved are not at risk of PGD (Lundorff et al., 2017), some individuals who develop complicated grief may also exhibit other psychological symptoms. Research shows a high co-occurrence of PGD with anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, depression and loneliness (Karatzias et al., 2022). Regarding physical symptoms, the relationship between PGD and somatisation has been pointed out by some studies, even suggesting that this type of symptomatology could be a criterion for the diagnosis of PGD in some populations (Killikelly et al., 2018).

To date, no study has examined this new disorder in the Spanish general population. Research on pathological grief is scarce, with studies reporting inconsistent findings due to the application of different diagnostic criteria and measurement instruments (Parro-Jiménez et al., 2021). Therefore, the main objectives of this study were to (a) to estimate the prevalence of PGD in Spain, (b) to identify the potential sociodemographic predictor variables, (c) to examine the relationship of ICD-11 PGD with the co-occurrence of common psychological disorders (i.e., depression, anxiety, somatisation, and post-traumatic stress), as well as with loneliness and

increased prescription medication and illicit drug use. In line with previous findings, it was hypothesised that sociodemographic factors such as gender, income, religion, and loss-related factors such as time since loss would be significantly associated with PGD. Additionally, it was anticipated that PGD would have a high co-occurrence with caseness of other mental disorders and drug overuse.

METHODS

Participants

A total of 1498 adults were recruited through an online research panel, using quota sampling methods to ensure representativeness in the sample of the national population in terms of age, gender, household income and political region (see Table 1). Data collection was conducted from 15th to 27th April 2021. A screening question was “At any time in your life, has someone close to you died?”. Following the time criterion of the ICD-11 for PGD, only those bereaved for more than 6 months ($n = 947$) were eligible for inclusion in PGD analyses.

Measures

ICD-11 prolonged grief disorder

The International Prolonged Grief Disorder Scale (IPGDS; Killikelly et al., 2020) is a 14-item self-report measure covering the criteria for the ICD-11 PGD. The first 12 items measure the two main clusters, the core symptoms (“I am longing or yearning for the deceased” and “I am preoccupied with thoughts about the deceased or circumstances of the death”) and the associated emotional pain (e.g., “I have trouble or just don’t want to accept the loss”, “I feel that I lost a part of myself”). Additionally, the last two items cover functional impairment (“Grief significantly interferes with my ability to work, socialise or function in everyday life”) and symptom deviation from the cultural norms (“My grief would be considered worse (e.g., more intense, severe, longer duration) than for others from my community or culture”). Participants rate the frequency of symptoms over the past week using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) “Not at all” to (5) “Always”. The IPGDS scoring algorithm can be applied to establish cases that meet the ICD-11 PGD criteria. PGD require at least one core symptom, one or more emotional symptoms, no less than one symptom of functional impairment, and exceeding the individual’s sociocultural norms. Endorsement of a symptom is indicated by a score of ≥ 3 (i.e., Sometimes, Often, or Always) according to the scoring of the scale developers (Killikelly et al., 2020). In the current study, the reliability of the 12 symptom items was excellent ($\alpha = .91$; $\omega = .92$).

Table 1
Sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the sample
(*N* = 947)

	<i>Participants</i>
Gender (female), <i>n</i> (%)	454 (47.9)
Age, mean (SD, range)	46.73 (12.49, 18–75)
Civil status, <i>n</i> (%)	
Single	305 (32.2)
Married/unmarried partner	523 (55.2)
Separated/divorced	95 (10)
Widower	24 (2.5)
Educational level, <i>n</i> (%)	
No formal education/primary	35 (3.7)
Secondary/High school	297 (31.4)
Technical qualification	145 (15.3)
University graduate/postgraduate	470 (49.6)
Religion, <i>n</i> (%)	
Catholic	510 (53.9)
Agnostic or atheist	397 (41.9)
Other	40 (4.3)
Urbanicity of residential location (urban), <i>n</i> (%)	798 (84.3)
Current economic activity, <i>n</i> (%)	
Full-time job/Part-time job	644 (68)
Unemployed/Pensioner	273 (28.8)
Student	30 (3.1)
Gross annual household income in euros (2019), <i>n</i> (%)	
Under 12,450	184 (19.4)
€12,450–20,200	216 (22.8)
€20,200–35,200	284 (30)
€35,200–60,000	206 (21.8)
Over €60,000	57 (6)
Mental health treatment, <i>n</i> (%)	
Actually	59 (6.2)
In the past	161 (17)
Actually, in the past	7 (0.7)
Never	700 (73.9)
Rather not answer	20 (2.1)

Note. SD = standard deviation.

Predictor variables

Sociodemographic data

Participants indicated sex (0 = male, 1 = female) and age in years. The age was collapsed into six categories: (1) 18–24 years; (2) 25–34 years; (3) 35–44 years; (4) 45–54 years; (5) 55–64 years; (6) 65 and over. Due to the low number of people between 18 and 24, the first two categories were collapsed for the non-descriptive analyses.

Living location

The area of residence was assessed as “Rural” (0) or “Urban” (1).

Educational background

Participants indicated the highest level of education completed by choosing from 7 categories

collapsed into 4 (0 = no education; 1 = compulsory primary/secondary only; 2 = high school and technical training; 3 = university and postgraduate studies).

Civil status

Participants were asked to indicate their current relationship status, which was collapsed into four categories (0 = single, 1 = married or cohabiting, 2 = separated or divorced, and 3 = widowed).

Religious identity

Participants indicated their religious identity by choosing from 8 options or writing it down if it was not listed among them. As most of the sample was Catholic, the options were collapsed into 3 categories for the analysis (0 = atheist, agnostic, 1 = catholic, and 2 = other religion).

Finance and employment

Participants indicated their gross annual income within five categories (up to €12,450; €12,450–20,200; €20,200–35,200; €35,200–60,000; €60,000 or more). Current employment status was measured using six categories which collapsed into three (0 = not working, 1 = full-time job/part-time job, student, 2 = unemployed/pensioner).

Mental health treatment

Participants specified whether they had received mental health treatment (psychological or pharmacological) by ticking as many as appropriate (0 = never, 1 = in the past, 2 = currently, 3 = prefer not to say). To be conservative, categories 0 and 3 were collapsed, and those who received treatment in the past and currently (*n* = 7) were grouped in category 2 (currently).

Substance use

Participants indicated whether they had increased their substance use (i.e., prescription medication and illicit drugs) in the last 2 weeks. The response options were 1 = any day, 2 = less than half of the days, 3 = More than half of the days, and 4 = almost every day. Responses 1 and 2 were collapsed to ‘No’ (0), and responses 3 and 4 to ‘Yes’ (1).

COVID-19-related variables

Participants were asked if they or a relative had been infected (0 = no, 1 = yes). In addition, they had to indicate if the loss was due to COVID-19 infection (0 = no, 1 = yes).

Bereavement period

As part of the IPGDS, participants indicated when their loss occurred. Seven response options were offered (0 = Less than 6 months ago, 1 = 6–12 months ago, 2 = 1–2 years ago, 3 = 2–5 years ago, 4 = 5–10 years ago, and 5 = 10–20 years ago. 6 = More than 20 years ago). The present study only included those bereaved for more than 6 months (due to the requirement that symptoms were present for ≥ 6 months in ICD-11).

Age of the deceased

Participants indicated in years the age of the deceased at the time of death. A multi-categorical variable was created, based on the observed range of ages, to represent the age group of the deceased (0 = under 34 years, 1 = 35–44 years, 2 = 45–55 years, 3 = 55–64 years and 4 = 65 and over).

Psychological variables

Depression

Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9; Kroenke et al., 2001) was used to measure symptoms of major depression disorder (MDD). On a 5-point Likert scale, participants indicated the frequency of nine symptoms over the last 2 weeks. The responses rated from “none of the days” (0) to “almost every day” (3). The total score was obtained by adding all the items. A cut-off score of ≥ 10 was used to detect probable depression cases with good sensitivity (.85) and specificity (.89) (Manea et al., 2012). The reliability in the present study was excellent ($\alpha = .92$; $\omega = .93$).

Anxiety

Generalised Anxiety Disorder 7-item Scale (GAD-7; Spitzer et al., 2006) was used to measure symptoms of generalised anxiety disorder over the last 2 weeks. Participants rated the frequency on a 4-point Likert scale from “none of the days” (0) to “almost every day” (3). The total score was obtained by adding the score of all items. The cut-off score of ≥ 10 was used to detect probable cases of GAD as it shows adequate sensitivity (.89) and specificity (.82) (Spitzer et al., 2006). The reliability in this study was excellent ($\alpha = .95$; $\omega = .95$).

Psychosomatic symptoms

The Patient Health Questionnaire 15 (PHQ-15; Kroenke et al., 2002) was used to measure over past week the frequency of the most prevalent somatic symptoms of DSM-IV somatisation disorder (APA, 2000). Responses

were given on a 3-point Likert scale, from “it does not bother me at all” (0) to “it bothers me a lot” (2). Two items, “menstrual pain” and “fainting”, were excluded from the addition for the total score (Cano-García et al., 2020). The recommended cut-off score of ≥ 15 was used to identify severe somatic symptoms (Kroenke et al., 2002). The reliability in the current study was good ($\alpha = .82$; $\omega = .85$).

Post-traumatic stress disorder

The International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ; Cloitre et al., 2018) was used as a self-report measure of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), as defined by the ICD 11. This instrument consists of six items assessing two symptoms from each cluster: reexperiencing, avoidance and feeling of threat, and three items measuring the functional impairment caused by the symptoms. All items are answered on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 0 (not at all) to 4 (extremely). A score of ≥ 2 (moderately) is considered the presence of the symptom. The diagnosis of PTSD requires traumatic exposure, at least one symptom from each cluster, and one or more indicators of functional impairment. The internal consistency in the current study was excellent ($\alpha = .90$; $\omega = .92$).

Loneliness

Three-item Loneliness Scale (TILS; Hughes et al., 2004) is a self-report measure that assesses the perception of social connectedness. The participants rated the frequency of three experiences on a 3-point Likert scale from “hardly ever” (1) to “often” (3). A total score was obtained by adding the items. A cut-off score of ≥ 6 was used to indicate loneliness (Shevlin et al., 2023). In this study, the reliability was good ($\alpha = .86$; $\omega = .86$).

Analytic procedure

We first estimated reliability for all the psychological scales using Cronbach alpha (α : Cronbach, 1951) and the more robust McDonald's Omega (ω : McDonald, 2013), with values greater than .70 being considered acceptable (Nunnally, 1994). Then ICD-11 criteria were applied to the PGDS scores to estimate the percentage of the total sample experiencing PGD and the percentage within those in bereavement. We examined with a Student's *t*-test whether there was a significant difference between males and females.

The main analyses were carried out in two stages using Mplus version 8.3 (Muthén & Muthén, 2018) with robust maximum likelihood estimation (Yuan & Bentler, 2000). Both stages involved first estimating unadjusted bivariate associations followed by multivariate analysis to produce adjusted estimates (Meyers et al., 2017). In the first stage,

all-categorical predictor variables were dummy-coded, and bivariate associations between the predictor variables and PGD were calculated using logistic regressions to derive unadjusted estimates. Results are reported as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals. Then, all predictor variables (see predictor variables in the measures section) were entered simultaneously into the multivariate binary logistic regression model to examine the unique effect of each predictor variable, and the associations were reported as adjusted ORs (AOR) with 95% confidence intervals. This produced adjusted estimates.

The second stage aimed to determine the degree to which PGD predicted the caseness on the other psychological disorders. The dependent variables (GAD-7, PHQ-9, PHQ-15, ITQ and TILS) were dichotomised using their cut-off scores to indicate the presence/absence of disorder or caseness. Increased use of prescription medication and illicit drugs dichotomised (yes, no) were also outputs. First, separate binary logistic regression models were performed with the PGD as the predictor and the dichotomous variables as the outcome variable. The bivariate associations were reported as ORs with 95% confidence intervals, and these were the unadjusted estimates. Second, a multivariate model was specified with PGD and sociodemographic variables (e.g., age, gender, income) as predictor variables, and all the dichotomised psychological outcome variables (caseness of GAD, PHQ-9, PHQ-15, ITQ, TILS) and drugs use were simultaneously regressed on these. The results are reported as AOR with 95% confidence intervals, and these were the adjusted estimates. The output results are available under request.

RESULTS

A 63.22% ($n = 947$) of the total sample reported having lost someone more than 6 months ago. Of these, 15.7% ($n = 149$) met the ICD-11 PGD criteria, which is a 9.9% prevalence of the total sample. There was a significant sex difference in ICD-11 PGD (males = 13.4%, females = 18.3%: $\chi^2(1) = 4.27, p = .039$).

The results from the binary logistic regression models used to predict PGD are reported in Table 2. The unadjusted ORs showed that being female, catholic, a widower, currently in psychological treatment, and having COVID-19 as the cause of the loss, were significant predictors, increasing the likelihood of meeting the criteria for PGD. Higher levels of education, higher incomes, and a longer time since loss happened withal decreased the likelihood of meeting the criteria for PGD. However, in the multivariate model, the adjusted effects showed that only catholic beliefs, higher income and a longer time since the loss happened remained significant. Besides, the age of the deceased over 65 emerged as a negative predictor.

Table 3 shows the unadjusted and adjusted ORs for PGD predicting caseness on the psychological outcomes and drug misuse. All the unadjusted ORs were large and statistically significant, indicating that meeting the criteria for PGD significantly increased the likelihood of screening positive for the psychological disorders measured. After adjustment for the demographic variables, the ORs remained significant and did not differ markedly in magnitude; the biggest difference was the attenuation of the OR for somatisation (PHQ-15), reducing from 4.932 to 3.811. In addition, the PGD predicted increased use of prescription and illicit drugs.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to identify the prevalence and predictors of ICD11 PGD in a nationally representative sample of Spain. It also examined the relationship of ICD-11 PGD with the co-occurrence of common psychological disorders, loneliness, increased prescription medication, and illicit drug use. Findings showed a 15.7% prevalence of ICD-11 PGD among individuals bereaved for 6 months or more, aligned with that found in the UK with the same diagnostic criteria and measurement (Shevlin et al., 2023), being higher than the adjusted prevalence of 11.0% reported by the largest meta-analysis ($N = 8035$) to date of bereaved people (Lundorff et al., 2017). Interestingly, the latter results showed significant variability in the estimates, ranging from 1.8 to 25.4%. The specific measurement instrument used in the studies accounted for the variability in prevalence rates; the pooled prevalence was either 20.5, 12.3, or 9.2%, depending on the particular instrument. Consequently, accurate prevalence estimates or comparisons across studies are not possible with such heterogeneity attributable to the measurement tool, and thus, standardisation of PGD measurement based on the current diagnostic criteria is necessary. Accordingly, Lundorff et al. (2017) stated that their findings "... clearly illustrates a need to align the field and develop a precise screening tool balancing between being theoretically sound, empirically well-validated, and practically useful in clinical settings" (p. 147). Hence, to maximise opportunities for globally based assessment that permits comparisons, the measurement instrument should be directly based on the ICD-11 symptoms and their diagnostic algorithm. A general agreement on the use of the measurement instrument in research would be desirable to allow comparison across cultures.

Although bivariate analyses showed several significant sociodemographic predictors of PGD, only catholic beliefs and income remained significant after their adjustment in the multivariate binary logistic regression model. Catholic religious beliefs doubled the likelihood of experiencing PGD compared to agnostic and

Table 2
Bivariate and multivariate binary logistic regression results predicting PGD

	<i>N</i>	<i>PGD, N (%)</i>	<i>Unadjusted OR</i>	<i>Adjusted OR</i>
Age				
<34	152	27 (17.8%)	—	—
35–44	208	27 (13%)	.691 (.387–1.234)	.751 (.380–1.484)
45–54	267	46 (17.2%)	.964 (.571–1.626)	1.227 (.646–2.329)
55–64	244	39 (16%)	.881 (.514–1.510)	.942 (.477–1.858)
>65	76	10 (13.2%)	.701 (.320–1.537)	.641 (.216–1.897)
Gender				
Male	493	66 (13.4%)	—	—
Female	454	83 (18.3%)	1.447 (1.018–2.058)*	1.311 (.875–1.964)
Living location				
Rural	149	24 (16.1%)	—	—
City	798	125 (15.7%)	.967 (.601–1.558)	.915 (.552–1.518)
Education				
No studies or mandatory	109	24 (22%)	—	—
High school/technical training	368	60 (16.3%)	.690 (.406–1.173)	.765 (.433–1.350)
Superior studies	470	65 (13.8%)	.568 (.337–.959)*	.764 (.420–1.391)
Religion				
Atheist, agnostic	397	43 (10.8%)	—	—
Catholic	510	100 (19.6%)	2.008 (1.367–2.950)*	2.067 (1.344–3.180)*
Other religion	40	6 (15%)	1.453 (.577–3.659)	.926 (.380–2.259)
Civil status				
Single	305	46 (15.1%)	—	—
Married, similar	523	85 (16.3%)	1.093 (.740–1.614)	1.323 (.813–2.153)
Separated, divorced	95	10 (10.5%)	.662 (.320–1.370)	.522 (.210–1.301)
Widower	24	8 (33.3%)	2.815 (1.139–6.958)*	2.473 (.748–8.179)
Income				
<€12,450	184	44 (23.9%)	—	—
€12,450–20,200	216	36 (16.7%)	.636 (.389–1.042)	.521 (.294–.925)*
€20,200–35,200	284	38 (13.4%)	.492 (.304–.795)*	.451 (.251–.812)*
€35,200–60,000	206	27 (13.1%)	.480 (.283–.814)*	.454 (.237–.969)*
>€60,000 €	57	4 (7%)	.240 (.082–.701)*	.197 (.058–.674)*
Laboral status				
No working	160	47 (17.2%)	—	—
Working/student	674	102 (15.1%)	.841 (.531–1.330)	1.238 (.706–2.170)
Disable and retired	113	19 (16.8%)	.953 (.503–1.807)	1.250 (.541–2.888)
Mental health treatment				
Never/no answer	720	101 (14%)	—	—
In the past	161	32 (19.9%)	1.520 (.979–2.362)	1.389 (.854–2.259)
Currently	66	16 (24.2%)	1.961 (1.075–3.577)*	1.957 (.976–3.923)
COVID-19 self				
Never	854	135 (15.8%)	—	—
Yes	93	14 (15.1%)	.944 (.519–1.715)	.895 (.453–1.765)
Covid-19 someone close				
No	611	52 (15.5%)	—	—
Yes	336	97 (15.9%)	1.031 (.714–1.487)	.846 (.558–1.281)
COVID caused the decease				
No	856	126 (14.7%)	—	—
Yes	91	23 (25.3%)	1.960 (1.178–3.261)*	.987 (.524–1.861)
Age of the deceased				
<34	44	8 (18.2%)	—	—
35–44	54	16 (29.6%)	1.895 (.723–4.965)	1.422 (.522–3.868)
45–54	58	7 (12.1%)	.618 (.206–1.856)	.383 (.126–1.162)
55–64	110	24 (21.8%)	1.256 (.516–3.057)	.737 (.283–1.917)
>65	676	92 (13.6%)	.709 (.319–1.573)	.393 (.168–.918)*
Time since the loss happened				
6–12 months	163	47 (28.8%)	—	—
1–2 years	128	25 (19.5%)	.599 (.345–1.041)	.494 (.266–.916)*
2–5 years	214	35 (16.4%)	.483 (.294–.793)*	.428 (.234–.781)*
5–10 years	195	21 (10.8%)	.298 (.169–.524)*	.271 (.140–.527)*
10–20 years	176	14 (8%)	.213 (.112–.406)*	.128 (.058–.283)*
>20 years	71	7 (9.9%)	.270 (.115–.632)*	.181 (.071–.461)*

* = Significant OR.

Table 3
Bivariate and multivariate binary logistic regression results

	GAD-7	PHQ-9	PHQ-15	ITQ	TILS	Prescribed drug use	Illicit drug use
Unadjusted OR							
PGD	6.23 (4.26–9.11)*	7.60 (5.21–11.09)*	4.93 (2.27–9.25)*	10.07 (6.44–15.76)*	4.22 (2.93–6.07)*	7.46 (4.00–13.92)*	6.28 (2.61–15.07)*
Adjusted OR							
PGD	6.29 (4.18–9.47)*	7.65 (5.11–11.46)*	3.81 (1.81–7.99)*	9.71 (6.13–15.4)*	4.25 (2.87–6.29)*	7.21 (3.77–13.78)*	6.31 (2.57–15.45)*
Age	.96 (.95–.97)*	.97 (.95–.983)*	.93 (.91–.96)*	.98 (.96–.99)*	.95 (.94–.97)*	.97 (.95–.99)*	.94 (.91–.97)*
Female	1.75 (1.22–2.5)*	1.36 (.98–1.90)	3.08 (1.32–7.18)*	.90 (.56–1.44)	1.63 (1.19–2.21)*	.63 (.33–1.17)	.32 (.13–.794)*
Income	.814 (.69–.95)*	.69 (.60–.80)*	.68 (.49–.94)*	.81 (.66–.99)*	.73 (.63–.83)*	.77 (.59–1.01)	.70 (.45–1.09)

Note: GAD-7 = Generalised Anxiety Disorder-7; ITQ = International Trauma Questionnaire; PGD = Prolonged Grief Disorder; PHQ-15 = Patient Health Questionnaire-15; PHQ-9 = Patient Health Questionnaire-9; TILS = Three-item Loneliness Scale. * = Significant OR.

atheist individuals. Similarly, a recent meta-analysis showed a positive association of religious beliefs with PGD (Heeke et al., 2017), suggesting that this may be due to negative religious coping (e.g., spiritual discontent, punishment from God or attributing the event to the devil's work). Caution should be taken with this particular result on catholic beliefs, as our study does not have a large sample of other religious beliefs and does not distinguish between positive and negative religious approaches. Additionally, the likelihood of having PGD decreases as income increases, with the lowest probability for people earning more than €60,000/year compared to those earning less than €12,450/year. This negative relationship between income and PGD has been consistently found in previous literature (Parro-Jiménez et al., 2021), and it is in line with other studies showing how lower income is related to worst outcomes in mental health and well-being (Vazquez et al., 2021).

It is worth mentioning that this study was conducted 15 months after the COVID-19 crisis was officially declared a pandemic by the WHO. Our results showed that pandemic-related variables, such as being infected with COVID-19, were not significant PGD predictors. COVID-19 as a cause of loss ceased to be a predictor of PGD once other variables were included in the analysis. Although some studies indicated that the prevalence of PGD is higher among people who have lost someone to COVID-19, other authors point out that PGD is precipitated by death occurring during the COVID-19 pandemic, not by the cause itself (Breen et al., 2022). This may be due to mourners being exposed to multiple concurrent stressors during the pandemic, increased social isolation and few opportunities for mourning rituals (Stroebe & Schut, 2021).

Among the loss-related predictors, the length of time since the loss was significant, consistent with previous findings showing a decreased likelihood of PGD as time went by (Shevlin et al. (2023)). The probability at 10 years is reduced to one-fifth compared to the odds at 6 and 12 months. This finding raises doubts about the controversial ICD11 time criterion of 6 months. This criterion was based on data indicating that meeting symptomatic criteria between 6 and 12 months post-bereavement was associated with significant impairment at 12–24 months (Prigerson et al., 2009). However, recent data show that the pattern of bereavement symptoms shows different trajectories in which time interacts with other variables (e.g., gender, education), changing symptomatology severity (Lundorff et al., 2020). In addition, the age of the deceased, being older than 65, was associated with a 60% decrease in the odds of PGD compared to when the deceased is younger than 34.

Furthermore, the logistic regression model performed to determine the degree to which PGD predicted the caseness of other psychological disorders showed that

meeting the criteria for PGD significantly increased the likelihood of meeting criteria for depression, anxiety, somatisation, PTSD and loneliness. The multivariate binary logistic regression model continued to indicate that PGD was a strong predictor, even after simultaneously including the sociodemographic variable PGD has been consistently linked in previous literature with other disorders, especially PTSD, anxiety, and depression (Boelen et al., 2010). The high comorbidity between some specific disorders might suggest that some single conditions have been split into multiple diagnoses, and as a result, these often coexist (Kotov et al., 2017). Especially in the case of PGD and PTSD, network analyses have pointed out that although the variability they exhibit may be due to common symptoms, they are distinct constructs with distinct boundaries (Karatzias et al., 2022). Previous factor analysis work has also shown that PGD, depression and anxiety represent distinct but highly correlated constructs (Boelen et al., 2010). There are overlapping but distinct symptom communities between loneliness and PGD (Shevlin et al., 2023), just as PGD shares symptoms with anxiety disorder, PTSD and MDD, such as worry, avoidance and sadness, respectively. Comorbidity provides relevant information on risk factors, pathological processes, and disease course (Kotov et al., 2017), with direct and valuable implications for clinical application.

Finally, PGD predicts a higher use of medication and illicit drugs, especially the former, and this is also influenced by age, as younger people are more likely to use illicit drugs. There are no gender differences in medication use, although results showed that women seem less likely to use illicit drugs. The increase in prescribed medication may be related to the fact that some medications are now prescribed for bereavement-related depression, although none have been designated as the “best” treatment (Maercker & Lalor, 2022). Some researchers suggest that antidepressant medication may be a valuable adjunct to bereavement treatment (Shear, 2022), however, findings indicate that although medication can decrease depressive symptoms, it does not improve the ongoing intensity of bereavement (Szuhany et al., 2021). Given the high comorbidity of PGD with other disorders, this increase in medication may be due to the coexistence of various diseases, and it seems relevant that this should be considered when assessing the efficacy of the chosen treatment, both psychological and pharmacological.

This study had some limitations. First, the screening question to assess bereavement did not capture the participant’s relationship with the deceased. Second, psychological measures were self-report rather than clinical interviews. Third, the cross-sectional design only allows us to assess the co-occurrence of all the psychological disorders rather than understanding their emergence due to

bereavement. However, this study also has strengths, as it is the first to examine the new PGD diagnostic category in the Spanish population. We also had a large representative sample and provided recent data on PGD, its predictors and its relationship with other psychological disorders.

In conclusion, grief is a universal process that everyone experiences at some point. It is essential to precisely define the characteristics of pathological grief and the variables that make people more vulnerable to developing it, researching samples from different cultures. Our study provides data from a representative population not previously measured by the PGDS which is based on ICD-11 PGD symptoms and its diagnostic algorithm, and the findings are comparable to results in other cultures obtained with the same instrument. The results show that approximately three in 20 bereaved adults exhibit PGD. Our findings point out to practitioners the core role of income, religious beliefs, age of the deceased and time since the loss in predicting maladaptive grief responses. Furthermore, our results revealed a relatively high co-occurrence of PGD with anxiety, depressive, somatic, post-traumatic stress, and loneliness disorders. This last finding suggests that overlapping symptoms between these disorders could be relevant and potential factors to assess for further treatment, especially given the increase in medication and illicit drugs related to PGD.

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